

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PRODUCTION ORGANIZATION AT LIGHT INDUSTRY AND IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN ECONOMY

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Annotation: The article considers possibilities of application of artificial intelligence technologies at the enterprises of light industry. The article discusses the possibilities of using artificial intelligence technologies at light industry enterprises. Ways of using machine vision technologies in the screening area and operations of stitching, cutting, sheathing and manual shearing are proposed.

Key words: organization of production, labor rationing, artificial intelligence, machine vision, intelligent timing. Artificial Intelligence in Production Organization at Light Industry

Introduction. The purpose of the article is to reveal the role of artificial intelligence in the development of the modern economy. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks: identify key methodological approaches to the concept of "artificial intelligence", determine the main characteristics and structure of the concept under study, and assess the level of influence of artificial intelligence on the labor market and educational services.

One of the most effective ways to solve these problems is the introduction of artificial intelligence technology into various spheres of economic activity.

Important elements are modules in which, on the basis of complex algorithms, the process of making a decision on a given problem takes place, as well as modules for transmitting information to the user and determining his reaction to the result obtained. Based on the analysis carried out, it can be concluded that intelligent systems are necessary, first of all, to solve problems associated with a

large amount of information, a high speed of its processing and a short time period for obtaining results.

Currently, clothing businesses and designers are faced with ever-increasing global competition and unpredictable fluctuations in demand. This pressure is forcing manufacturers to continually improve the productivity of their manufacturing process to deliver the finished product as quickly as possible to minimize supply disruptions to retail. However, consistent and optimal solutions are difficult to achieve in an unclear and dynamic production environment. Consequently, in response to the need, the companies began to develop a technologically advanced automated platform based on artificial intelligence for the garment industry to speed up the production process, to make finding and matching the exact design color for the finished product more affordable and faster in real time.

The industry must evolve rapidly to meet the need to provide the right products at the right price, at the right time, and to the right customers through improved and technological processes. Moreover, such a modernization should go not only from the side of e-commerce, but also from the side of the production process, which will improve the communication of customers, designers and the production itself.

While traditional color tolerances were made from numerical color descriptions using “tool tolerance systems,” this method tended to have many false positives compared to visual checks, resulting in delays in the approval process due to the need careful human intervention.

Companies are developing a feature for artificial intelligence to help improve the accuracy and efficiency of instrumental resilience.

The future platform will be able to serve as an aggregator, including computer vision and machine learning methods. The platform will receive requests, and the AI system will provide important information and advice on these requests in real time. [3]

The procedure is supposed to work like this:

A textile or yarn expert will first visually inspect all individual batches that have been produced. Operators enter color measurements and tolerances for all batches into the software to train the AI system. The system can then be tested on new batches to automatically set AI tolerances by training the system to determine which samples pass and fail. Samples from each batch can be checked for quality using a platform to set the tolerance limit. Any samples outside the tolerance range are discarded.

In real life, this app can help both textile manufacturers and their customers improve the speed and accuracy of ordering and color matching processes.

The main trend in the development of industrial production in the last decade has been the use of integrated automation systems. At the same time, enterprises used solutions that allow them to control the entire production cycle and integrate computer systems into it, which ensured the flexibility of technological processes and the possibility of a quick change of types of products. These solutions required the introduction of powerful computer technology and the re-equipment of production, which entailed serious capital investments.

However, the development of artificial intelligence technologies made it possible to eliminate these serious shortcomings and made it possible to create automation systems of a fundamentally new level that allow analyzing the situation in real time and maintaining operability when changing control objectives, unforeseen changes in the properties of a controlled object or environmental parameters. A system based on the principles of artificial intelligence is capable of instantly changing the control algorithm and looking for optimal and effective solutions.

Today artificial intelligence can be applied in all business verticals and at all levels [1,2]:

- 1) at the design level - to improve the efficiency of new product development, automate the selection and assessment of suppliers, when analyzing the requirements for spare parts and parts;
- 2) at the production level - to improve business processes and coordinate various production systems;
- 3) at the logistics level - to improve the planning of transportation routes, reduce the delivery time of raw materials and ensure their predictability, as well as track shipments and the delivery process at all stages;
- 4) at the promotion level - to predict the volume of support and maintenance services, manage pricing and analyze customer satisfaction with product quality.

Artificial intelligence technologies are already used in various sectors of the national economy: in medicine, based on processing a large amount of data, they allow a timely diagnosis of a patient with high accuracy, in industry - to completely automate harmful and dangerous production, in various fields of agriculture - to detect plant diseases, classify and identify weeds, manage water resources and soil, and predict climate. These technologies are gaining more and more importance in light industry.

To obtain an image, a machine vision camera (CAM-CIC-5MR / 5000R) is installed above the grading table, the data from which is transmitted to a computer and processed using specialized software Adaptive vision. Using Deep Learning technology, the software is able to learn from “good” and “bad” examples, and then, by receiving an image, signal the presence of a marriage.

Machine vision systems provide not only the detection of defects, contactless comparison of the shape and appearance of products with a reference sample to detect deviations from the specified product characteristics, but also an assessment of their sizes, classification by types of defects, maintaining statistics, as well as saving and issuing work results for a given period with the ability to print reports. [4]

The economic effect from the introduction of the technology will be obtained as a result of a decrease in scrap by 19.99%, which will increase the profit of the enterprise by at least 3%. Thus, the implementation of the project for the introduction of machine vision at the quality control area in order to increase the efficiency of the enterprise is expedient. The payback period of the project will be 0.41 years.

Machine vision technology is applicable for tracking the accuracy and correctness of manual and machine-hand operations in the areas of sewing, cutting, sheathing and manual shearing. With the help of this technology, it is possible to recognize the type of operation carried out by an employee, determine the time spent on the operation, track irrational or unnecessary labor practices, and also determine the location of workers and their movement across the production area.

In order to implement this event, it is necessary to install 4 Geovision GV-EFER3700 cameras, which form images of the production area (panoramic), individual workplaces (enlarged) and other areas. An intelligent network based on artificial intelligence, trained in fine motor skills of the hands of the performer of the operation, recognizes a person by face and gestures. The information from the cameras goes to the computer, where it is processed with the help of software. The controller-operator downloads a map of the production area, highlighting its border, workplaces of interest, areas of special interest. The map also acts as a 2D background on which the location of workers and their personal data in the system are visualized. The operator-controller generates reports on timing with the movements of a particular worker between specified zones. The timing of the operations performed is automatically recorded by the system and issued in the form of a report at the request of the operator.

As a result of the constant intelligent timing of the actions of workers through the optimization of working methods and actions, their production will increase by at least 1%. Since the employees will be monitored continuously, the

loss of time as a result of violation of labor discipline will be reduced (according to the company, they make up 3% of working time). Also, as a result of observations, a base of optimal labor practices will be formed, which will allow in the future to adjust the time norms for their implementation.

In the course of the study of the influence of artificial intelligence on the modern labor market, the following conclusions were drawn: [5,6]

1. The introduction of artificial intelligence in various spheres of economic activity will lead to a decrease in the role of man and his significant displacement as a labor resource. First of all, this will affect such areas, which are based on a repeatable algorithm of actions. Examples include the following areas:

- Tourism. Artificial intelligence can replace the work of an entire travel company, performing the functions of finding the best tour for a client, issuing all the necessary documents, providing tickets, hotel accommodation, providing excursions and entertainment, promptly informing customers about promotions and discounts, etc.

- Financial sector. Artificial intelligence will perform various banking operations, make transactions in the securities market, and insurance operations.

- Marketing, where artificial intelligence will research consumer preferences.

2. The use of artificial intelligence in the economy will lead to the development of freelancing. However, this concept itself will be modified.

An individual will look for remote work not according to the principle "what you like", but according to the principle "what is."

3. Specialists in areas primarily related to artificial intelligence will be in demand: biology (in the study of the structure and function of the human brain), computer science, linguistics, mathematics, psychology, robotics. [7]

4. Creative labor specialists will be in great demand on the market. And the higher the professional level of an artist, actor, program host, artist, the harder it will be to replace it with artificial intelligence, since imagination, intuition and emotions are not available to it.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I would like to note that artificial intelligence, becoming an integral element of the economy, provides the maximum effect when solving various problems with minimal costs. The process of introducing artificial intelligence will lead to changes in the labor market will increase the relevance of professions where it is impossible to simulate emotions, feelings and impressions.

However, its use in the textile industry has not yet gained wide acceptance. Nevertheless, competition and the desire to reduce production costs are the main reasons for the introduction of artificial intelligence in light industry enterprises.

As people become more and more "impatient", shortening lead times is key to ensuring optimal delivery times. This is why many companies have taken it a step further and used the entire process to improve the speed and efficiency of the supply chain. Things like finding materials, yarns, and matching original colors in designs.

The main applications of artificial intelligence by light industry enterprises are using big data analytics. Thus, artificial intelligence makes a valuable contribution to the light industry revolution, including the integration of digital processes into production, quality improvement, cost reduction, information processing, statistical control of production processes and, as a result, obtaining computer-integrated production.

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